

Impact of future scenarios of climate change on lignin dynamics in soil: A case study in a Mediterranean savannah

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Source vegetation is the main driver of lignin dynamics in a Mediterranean *dehesa*.
- Enhanced and accelerated lignin decomposition under the tree canopy
- Contrariwise, more retarded lignin degradation in open grassland
- Warming and rainfall exclusion causes oxidative alteration especially of LS-units.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Lignin is an abundant and recalcitrant biopolymer of major relevance as soil organic matter (SOM) component playing a significant role in its stabilization. In this work, a factorial field experiment was established, where three climatic treatments (W, warming; D, drought; W + D, warming + drought), mimicking future climate change scenarios were installed over five years in a Mediterranean savannah "*dehesa*", accounting for its landscape diversity (under the tree canopy and in open grassland). A combination of analytical pyrolysis (Py-GC/MS) and the study of biogeochemical proxies based on lignin monomers is used for the direct detection of lignin-derived phenols and to infer possible shifts in lignin dynamics in soil. A total of 27 main lignin-derived methoxyphenols were identified, exhibiting different patterns and proportions, mainly driven by the effect of habitat, hence biomass inputs to SOM. An accelerated decomposition of lignin moieties –(exhibited by higher LG/LS and Al/K + Ac ratios)– is particularly exacerbated by the effect of all climatic treatments. There is also an overall effect on increasing lignin oxidation of side chain in syringyl units, especially under the tree canopy due to the alteration in biomass degradation and potential stimulation of enzyme activities. Conversely, in open grassland these effects are slower since the microbial community is expected to be already adapted to harsher

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conditions. Our findings suggests that climate change-related temperature and soil moisture deviations impact soil lignin decomposition in *dehesas* threatening this productive Mediterranean agroecosystem and affecting the mechanism of soil carbon storage.

1. Introduction

Soil organic matter (SOM) constitutes the most crucial and complex soil component, playing an essential role in chemical, physical and biological properties, including soil structure, productivity, and erodibility (Feng and Simpson, 2011; Cotrufo and Lavallee, 2022). The SOM also accounts for one of the major pools of soil organic carbon (SOC) in terrestrial ecosystems (Lal, 2007), with several pools and fractions showing varying degrees of decomposition and stability (von Lützwow et al., 2007). This molecular complexity conditions soils' capacity of acting both as source and sink of carbon, especially given the growing concern over climate change. Therefore, it is imperative to improve the understanding in SOM dynamics in this context.

Soils within Mediterranean regions, more specifically in the Iberian Peninsula, exhibit some particularities at this respect. Generally, Mediterranean soils show lower depth/profile development, often associated with rock outcrops (Anastasiou et al., 2015). It is frequent to find soils developed on calcareous parent material and containing large amounts of carbonates, which implies larger proportions of inorganic C relative to the SOC (Orgiazzi et al., 2018). Due to the abovementioned characteristics, Mediterranean soils receive a relatively higher negative impact on SOC content as elevated temperatures are known to accelerate SOC decay rate, thus increasing C emission (Ondrasek et al., 2019). Among the most representative ecosystems found in this context, Mediterranean savannahs, commonly known as *dehesas*, cover about 3.5–4 million ha in Spain and Portugal and are distinguished by a sparse canopy of mature cork or holm oak trees, under which a diverse understory of grasses and shrubs grows (Bugalho et al., 2011). These agroforestry ecosystems are subjected to marked seasonality with severe drying cycling and intense solar radiation (Bolle, 2003). Furthermore, these ecosystems harbour microclimate conditions beneath tree canopies, which directly affect plant development and SOM contributions and dynamics (da Silva et al., 2021).

Additionally, the Mediterranean climate can be thought of as an ecotone, a climate that transitions between the subtropical-desert and the temperate area conditions (Rodó and Comín, 2001). Mediterranean regions of Europe are best defined by their distinct climate, with cold humid winters and warm dry summers. Nevertheless, it is anticipated that these climatic elements would worsen these conditions: as stated in the MedECC report (2020), the Mediterranean region is warming 20 % faster than the global average. In addition, the actual scenario of global warming predicts an increase of temperatures (2–4 °C) that will reduce precipitation by up to 30 % in Southern Europe. These changes have been already studied to be reflected in the growth of the oak trees (López-Tirado and Hidalgo, 2016), the composition and timing of flowering grasslands (Hidalgo-Gálvez et al., 2022), and in SOM molecular structure (San-Emeterio et al., 2023a). The latter is expected to cause substantial changes in carbon sequestration potential and SOC dynamics accounting for its mitigation role (Nair, 2011). In this sense, soils in *dehesas* are aimed at enhancing the soil's resilience by disentangling the diverse organic forms of C, special attention driven to the alteration of recalcitrant compounds' stability i.e. lignin moieties (Jastrow et al., 2007; Dungait et al., 2008).

Mechanisms behind SOC storage are partly driven by SOM chemical structure, accounting for components of higher recalcitrance and complex structure such as plant-derived biopolymers like lignin (Jiménez-González et al., 2017). Lignin is a three-dimensional biopolymer synthesized by plants by linking structural units of hydroxycinnamyl, coniferyl and sinapyl alcohols, resulting in their respective monomeric units: cinnamyl or *p*-hydroxyphenyl (LH), vanillyl or guaiacyl (LG) and

syringyl (LS) (Adler, 1977). Contributing up to 30 % of vascular plant biomass (Hedges and Mann, 1979), the proportion of the different lignin monomers in SOM depends on the type of biomass inputs (Fengel and Wegener, 2011). Further insight into the lignin's state of decomposition can be gained by taking into account the functional groups of the lignin units, such as aldehyde, ketone, and acid substitutions, as biochemical indicators (Kögel-Knabner, 1986; Lupoi et al., 2015). The distribution of lignin in soils is affected by local microclimatic conditions, e.g., soil temperature and moisture (Amelung et al., 1999; Thevenot et al., 2010). Previous studies have shown that an increase in soil temperature may increase plant C contributions to soil and enhance SOM decomposition in the short term, especially of recalcitrant compounds (Ding et al., 2019; Angst et al., 2021). Moreover, the activity of some key soil enzymes and fungal communities related to lignin degradation, are generally enhanced under warming and water scarcity (Feng et al., 2008; Schmitt and Glaser, 2011; Wang et al., 2012). Nevertheless, it is mandatory to overcome these changes covering highly recalcitrance SOM compounds in a representative agroecosystem soil within the Mediterranean region.

The aim of this study is to evaluate how lignin will evolve in soils from Mediterranean savannahs and respond to induced climate change. For this purpose, we have applied analytical pyrolysis coupled with gas-chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS), which has been proven quite useful and handy for characterizing SOM at a molecular level and assessing environmental changes (San-Emeterio et al., 2023a). We hypothesize that there will be significant alterations in lignin dynamics, more specifically promoting its degradation, under future scenarios of climate change. We expect to find stronger effects of warming and rainfall exclusion on the lignocellulosic dynamics in open grassland compared to beneath the tree canopy. This assumption is based on the second hypothesis that trees will buffer the impact of these climatic abiotic stress on lignin decomposition and involved processes. Also, we aimed at checking our assumptions by calculating biogeochemical, lignin-related proxies and correlate them with microclimate measurements. To our knowledge, this is the first study that provides a detailed approach about the impact of climate change (including warming and drought) on lignin signature in a Mediterranean ecosystem, under experimental field conditions along with the application of a direct analytical technique such as Py-GC/MS. The current study's findings may contribute to our understanding of how lignin might potentially respond to future climate change and provide the basis for using lignin as a biomarker to trace SOM dynamics.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Site description

The study was carried out in an evergreen oak *dehesa* in Pozoblanco, Córdoba, Southwestern Spain (38° 20' 47.8" N, 4° 48' 57.0" W), located at an elevation of 675 m above sea level. The climate in this area is dry Mediterranean-type with warm, dry summers and humid, cold winters. The annual precipitation in the zone is 439 mm yr⁻¹, mostly occurring from October to May, and mean annual temperature is 15.7 °C (data from the 2017–2021 on average retrieved from IFAPA meteorological station, Hinojosa del Duque, <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/agriculturaypesca/ifapa/riaweb/web/estacion/14/102>). The area is characterized by the scattered presence of evergreen oak (*Quercus ilex* subsp. *ballota*), with a mean density of 14.5 ± 1.3 trees ha⁻¹ (covering approx. 20 % of the surface) and a dense herbaceous layer (covering >80 %) dominated by annual native pasture species such as *Hordeum murinum*

(L.), *Senecio vulgaris* (L.), *Bromus madritensis* (L.) and *Sinapis alba* (L.). More details on the vegetation cover are depicted in [Hidalgo-Gálvez et al. \(2022\)](#). Soil is classified as Eutric Cambisol ([IUSS, 2014](#)), characterized by a sandy-loamy texture (74.2 % sand; 19.0 % silt; 6.9 % clay). The soil is usually shallow, reaching a maximum depth of 50 cm. Soil pH is slightly acidic to neutral (ca. 6.2) with absence of carbonates.

2.2. Experimental design and soil sampling

The experimental design was a full factorial field experiment started in autumn 2016, where the main factors were canopy cover and climate scenarios. A total of 36 experimental plots (4 × 6 m) were installed at a minimum distance of 20 cm, but 32 were selected for this experiment (2 canopy covers × 4 climatic scenarios × 4 replicates). The effect of canopy designated hereafter as ‘habitat’ was under *Quercus ilex* canopy (tree) and open grasslands between trees (open). In each plots, four climatic scenarios were mimicked in the two selected habitat (under the tree canopy and in open grassland): 1) ‘control’ (C), without any manipulation; 2) ‘warming’ (W), using methacrylate open top chambers (OTCs, [Marion et al., 1997](#)) following a hexagonal design and covering an area of 0.65 m² to force an increase of 2–3 °C; 3) ‘drought’ (D), using six methacrylate rainfall-exclusion shelters (2.5 × 2.5 × 1.5 m; 20° inclination) intercepting 30 % of the precipitation. Finally, a combined 4) ‘warming and drought’ (W + D) was combined in order to assess simultaneously the effect of both climatic stressors. These climatic scenarios were set based on climate forecasting models according to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change the Mediterranean area (SRES A-2 model by the [IPCC, 2022](#)). More details about the experimental design implemented in the field is shown in Fig. S1.

Soils were sampled in summer 2021, 5 years since the experiment started. Samples were taken from the first 10 cm of the soil with an auger, considering a total of five samples per experimental unit then later combined in a composite sample. Soil samples were air-dried, sieved to fine earth (< 2 mm) and stored at room temperature. Prior to any analysis, all samples were finely ground and homogenized using a planetary mixer ball mill (Retsch GmbH Mod. MM 400, Haan, Germany).

Air temperature was registered at ground level hourly with a resolution of 0.1 °C using HOBO MX2201 data loggers (Onset Computer, Bourne, MA, USA). Volumetric water content in the soil was periodically assessed using a PR2 humidity probe (Delta-T Devices Ltd., Cambridge, UK). It is connected to a permanent access tube of 40 cm depth and it records moisture values at intervals of 10 cm. Further details on the data acquisition regarding these two environmental features are given in [Hidalgo-Gálvez et al. \(2022\)](#). Analysed data showed in this study corresponds to the sampling date of this study and a maximum depth of 10 cm, according to our soil sampling strategy.

2.3. Pyrolysis-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS)

Direct pyrolysis–gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) analysis was performed using a double-shot pyrolyzer (model 2020i; Frontier Laboratories Ltd., Fukushima, Japan) attached to a GC Agilent 6890 N (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) and an Agilent 5973 mass spectrometer. Soil samples were weighed (15 mg) in small ultra-alloy deactivated pyrolysis capsules and pyrolyzed into a preheated micro-furnace at 400 °C for 1 min. The evolved gases were directly transferred into the GC/MS for analysis. The gas chromatograph was equipped with a low polar-fused silica (5 % phenyl-methylpolysiloxane) capillary column Agilent J&W HP-5 ms UI, of 30 m × 250 μm × 0.25 μm film thickness. The oven temperature was held at 50 °C for 1 min and then increased to 100 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹, from 100 °C to 300 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹ and stabilised at 300 °C for the last 10 min. The carrier gas used was He at a controlled flow of 1 mL min⁻¹ and the total chromatographic time was 32,50 min. The mass spectra were acquired in the scan mode with positive ionization energy at 70 eV. To ensure a clean system, to

evaluate contamination and that no carryover occurred from successive samples, method blanks using hexane were included every three samples.

The identification and relative quantification of the pyrolysis products was done by: 1) selecting specific ion (*m/z*) chromatograms for major compound series since pyrolysis preserves the structure of the original building blocks (LG, LS, and LH) and their chemical counterparts ([Miralles et al., 2015](#); [Almendros et al., 2018](#); [San-Emeterio et al., 2023b](#)); 2) comparing mass spectra with own lignin libraries and reported in the literature for lignin and plant material ([Ralph and Hatfield, 1991](#)) and 3) by comparison with stored commercial mass spectra NIST 14 and Wiley 7 libraries. A detailed list of all compounds released by Py-GC/MS, in addition to the methoxyphenols, are available in [San-Emeterio et al. \(2023a\)](#).

2.4. Biogeochemical proxies' calculation

Several molecular proxies were applied to assess the source and degradation of organic matter in soil from the relative abundance of the lignin-derived compounds released directly after pyrolysis. LG and LS units accounts for all identified guaiacyl and syringyl units, respectively. Based on this general classification, non-oxidized alkyl-phenols were differentiated according to the alkyl side chains in Ph-C₁ (4-methyl LG & LS units), Ph-C₂ (4-ethyl and 4-vinyl LG & LS units) and Ph-C₃ (4-propyl and 4-allyl LG & LS units). Conversely, the VSC semiquantitative approach was applied to alternatively classify methoxyphenols as follows: V is vanillyl-type (vanillin, acetovanillone, and vanillic acid), S is syringyl-type (syringaldehyde, acetosyringone and homosyringone) and C is cinnamyl-type (ferulic acid). In order to estimate lignin decay in SOM, S/V and C/V ratios were calculated. These ratios are used to characterize the type of lignin in SOM according to the vegetation source: a higher C/V ratio indicates a higher contribution of non-woody vs. woody plant material and a higher S/V ratio indicates a higher contribution of angiosperm vs. gymnosperm plant material ([Hedges and Mann, 1979](#)). The S/V ratio has been also used as a valid proxy for selective degradation of syringyl lignin as opposed to vanillyl lignin ([Heidke et al., 2019](#)).

Also, the acid-to-aldehyde ratio of vanillyl, (Ac/Al)_V and syringyl units, (Ac/Al)_S were calculated as indicator of lignin oxidation status ([Ziegler et al., 1986](#); [Amelung et al., 1999](#)), including the following compounds: acetoguaiacone and acetovanillone/vanillin (V), acetosyringone/syringaldehyde (S). During lignin oxidative degradation aldehydes are converted to acids and an increase in the Ac/Al_{V,S} ratios points to stronger side-chain oxidation and to increasing lignin decomposition ([Kalbitz et al., 2006](#)). It should be noted here that the proxies calculated here are somewhat derived from those based on lignin phenols isolated by the conventional CuO oxidation method, hence it aimed at complementing the pyrolysis-based indexes.

2.5. Data analysis

Normality and homoscedasticity were checked prior to any statistical analysis using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the Levene test, respectively. A factorial analysis of variance (Two-way ANOVA) was performed when the assumptions of normal distribution and homogeneity of variance were met, followed by Tukey post-hoc tests. When data did not meet the normality or homogeneity requirements even after a log transformation was applied, non-parametric Scheirer-Ray-Hare test was used for treatment comparisons and their interactions along with a Dunn post-hoc test for multiple non-parametric comparisons. These statistical analyses were made with a 95 % confidence level using the statistical package SPSS 20.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). RStudio (version 2022.03.0), “rcompanion” and “FSA” packages were used for Scheirer-Ray-Hare test ([Mangiafico, 2020](#)). Spearman's rank correlation was performed to visualize the statistical dependence between selected lignocellulosic proxies and measured microclimatic factors: soil

temperature and soil water content. Correlation matrices were sorted by type of habitat and climatic treatment. R packages “corrplot” and “ggpubr” were used for graphical representation of correlation (Wei and Simko, 2021).

3. Results

A total of 27 lignin-derived methoxyphenols were identified by Py-GC/MS. These included guayacil (LG) and syringyl (LS) units and their methyl-, ethyl-, vinyl-, propenyl- and aceto- derivatives, as well as *p*-hydroxyphenyl (LH)-lignin units (vinylphenol and phenol, *x*-methyl) (Table 1). An example of the specific ion traces of each methoxyphenol is shown in Fig. 1, where labels in grey correspond to other non-lignin compounds that also include mass fragments with this particular *m/z*.

The LG- units were found the most abundant lignin methoxyphenols in the soil pyrolyzates (Table 1). These units, along with the LS- units were significantly more abundant under the tree canopy ($8.1 \pm 0.4\%$ vs $6.5 \pm 0.7\%$ in open grassland; $p = 0.021$) Sorted by each habitat-type, it can be seen that, under the tree canopy, the ‘W’ and ‘D’ treatments had a substantially lower abundance of LS- units than the control plots ($7.0 \pm 0.6\%$ and $7.1 \pm 0.7\%$, respectively; $p = 0.037$). For LH- units, the effects of climate treatments within each habitat exerted considerable differences, but no general differences were detected between habitats. In this sense, it seems that LH- units are more sensitive to the climate scenarios showing reverse trends to those for LG- & LS- units: a significant increase, rather than a decrease, in the ‘D’ and ‘W + D’ plots (Table 1). These effects are observed in a significant relative decrease in control plots ($1.5 \pm 1.0\%$ both in open and tree habitats). On the other hand, there is a noticeable increase underneath the tree canopy, which also includes the ‘W’ treatment.

3.1. Lignocellulose proxies

Several proxies were calculated to explain the ongoing processes of SOM transformation, specifically regarding lignocellulose dynamics (Fig. 2). The lignin-guayacil units/polysaccharides (LG/PS) ratio showed general increasing values under the tree canopy (average 0.90 ± 0.09 vs 0.67 ± 0.08 in open habitat, $p = 0.002$; Fig. 2A). In both habitat-types, significant lower values were observed in ‘D’ plots compared to the rest of treatments ($p = 0.041$, Table 2).

Relative lower values for the LG/LS ratio under the tree canopy ($p = 0.035$, Table 2), in contrast to the greater values in open grassland (2.5 ± 0.3 vs 2.1 ± 0.1 , Fig. 2B). The effect of the climatic treatments is only observed under the tree canopy, with significant higher LG/LS values under the climatic treatments (Fig. 2B; Table 2, $p = 0.049$). Although no statistically different, in open grassland consistently LG/LS higher values were also found in all three climatic treatments compared to control. The relative abundance of lignin compounds with different alkyl side chain lengths (Ph-C₁, Ph-C₂ and Ph-C₃) was not affected by the habitat (Figs. 2C-E). Thereby, the calculated Ph-C₁ + C₂/Ph-C₃ ratio only showed effects among climate scenarios, again with diverse trends according to the habitats (Fig. 2F): whereas under the tree canopy the lower value was found in the ‘W’ treatment (1.7 ± 0.2), in open grassland this effect was observed for ‘D’ and ‘W + D’ (1.9 ± 0.1 and 2.2 ± 0.2 , respectively).

Higher Al/K + Ac ratios were found significantly higher in open habitat ($p = 0.012$, Table 2; Fig. 2G). In the open habitat, lower values are consistently spotted for ‘W’ and ‘D’ treatments compared to the control plots (0.41 ± 0.04 in both treatments compared to 0.75 ± 0.17 in control). These differences are smoother under the tree canopy, where significant lower values were only found for the ‘W + D’ treatment (0.29 ± 0.03 , $p = 0.020$; Table 2).

Results from the syringyl/vanillyl (S/V) and the cinnamyl/vanillyl (C/V) ratios are presented in Fig. 3A. Main differences are observed in the C/V ratio, with relatively lower values in all climatic treatments compared to the control plots, except for the ‘D’ plot under the tree

canopy, which did not show any significant differences (Fig. 3a). On the other hand, S/V ratio did not show major differences, although a greater S/V value was observed in the control plots for open habitat. It is remarkable how neither of the treatments were greatly affected by the habitat, whilst some differentiation was observed in both control plots. Finally, a further step on the assessment of lignin degradation was made by the calculation of the acid-to-aldehyde ratios for the vanillyl (Ac/Al_V) and syringyl units (Ac/Al_S) (Fig. 3B). Mean values of Ac/Al_V ranged from 3.7 to 1.0, and the Ac/Al_S from 3.3 to 1.4. Regarding the Ac/Al_V values, a clear differentiation was noted between both habitats, showing significant greater values under the tree canopy (2.9 ± 0.4 compared to open 1.7 ± 0.3 , $p = 0.001$). However, a significant distinction was exerted by an increase of this index in the ‘W + D’ treatment (3.7 ± 0.3 , $p = 0.001$). Additionally, the Ac/Al_S showed less variation with changes in the environmental factors, despite greater values are found for the ‘D’ treatment in both habitats. Lastly, under the tree canopy although no statistically significant, Ac/Al_S values under the ‘W’ treatment were lower than in the control, opposed to what is observed in open grassland (Fig. 3B).

3.2. Microclimate influence on lignin dynamics

Fig. 4 displays a set of correlation matrices between the two environmental parameters: chosen lignin proxies, arranged by habitat type and climatic treatment, and soil temperature and water content (labeled as ‘soil.temp’ and ‘soil.moist’, respectively). Generally speaking, the link between soil temperature and water content in control plots from both environments.

With the exception of the warming plots in open grassland, all habitats and scenarios showed a tendency for C/V and S/V, the two climatic treatments, to be positively correlated. With the sole exception of warming, the Spearman correlation in open grassland shows a negative association between soil temperature and S/V and C/V. Additionally, the positive association between Ac/Al_S and soil temperature is indicated. Soil water content positively correlated with Ac/Al_S in the ‘D’ and ‘W + D’ treatments, and with Ac/Al_V in the ‘W’ and ‘D’ treatments. In warming plots, there is a negative relationship between the S/V and Ac/Al_S, but in drought plots, there is a positive relation with Ac/Al_V.

When it comes to tree habitat, the relationship between soil temperature and C/V is negative in both ‘W’ and ‘W + D’. Furthermore, the S/V and Ac/Al_S indices are also negatively impacted by the warming effect. Finally, a side effect demonstrating a negative association between soil moisture and Ac/Al_V under the ‘W’ treatment is presented. It is evident that the ‘D’ treatment resulted in a strong negative association with Ac/Al_V and a positive correlation with S/V and soil water content. Additionally, under ‘W + D’ there is a positive correlation between S/V and C/V and soil water content.

4. Discussion

Attending to the LG- and LS- lignin moieties, soils under the tree canopy showed a notably higher proportion, which leads us to firstly attribute it to the differences in litter inputs to SOM (Vancampenhout et al., 2009). Overall, no significant differences were found between the climate scenarios; however, when these differences were sorted within each habitat, it was found that under drought and induced warming there was a decreasing percentage of LS-units beneath the tree canopy. Previous studies have found that these units decompose faster LG-type, possibly due to a higher degree of cross-linking between monomers (Allard, 2006; Zaccone et al., 2008; Bao et al., 2017). Hence, our precursory findings lead to an easier, more rapid degradation of lignin monomers under the tree canopy.

Simultaneously, the relatively higher abundance observed under control plots regardless the habitat points out to a relative preferential accumulation of lignin (Thevenot et al., 2010). Low proportion of LH-units corresponds to the abovementioned composition of vegetation

Table 1
Methoxyphenols identified and released by Py-GC/MS of bulk soils (% relative to the total abundance). Values are presented as means ($n = 4$) \pm standard error (SE). Uppercase letters indicate differences between habitats; lowercase letters indicate differences among climatic treatments (Two-Way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$).

N°	Methoxyphenols	Lignin type	m/z	Open				Tree			
				C	W	D	W + D	C	W	D	W + D
1	2-methoxyphenol (guaiacol)	LG	81, 109, 124	2.6 \pm 0.2	2.4 \pm 0.1	2.6 \pm 0.2	2.8 \pm 0.3	2.2 \pm 0.2	2.6 \pm 0.3	2.7 \pm 0.3	2.6 \pm 0.4
2	2-methoxy-4-methylphenol (methylguaiacol)	LG	95, 123, 138	1.4 \pm 0.3	1.6 \pm 0.1	1.3 \pm 0.2	1.1 \pm 0.2	1.6 \pm 0.5	1.3 \pm 0.3	1.8 \pm 0.1	1.3 \pm 0.2
3	4-ethyl-2-methoxyphenol (ethylguaiacol)	LG	122, 137, 152	1.2 \pm 0.2	0.85 \pm 0.25	0.93 \pm 0.17	0.80 \pm 0.23	0.98 \pm 0.07	0.98 \pm 0.04	1.1 \pm 0.1	1.0 \pm 0.1
4	4-ethenyl-2-methoxyphenol (vinylguaiacol)	LG	107, 135, 150	2.6 \pm 0.3	2.5 \pm 0.3	2.6 \pm 0.2	3.1 \pm 0.3	2.1 \pm 0.2	2.1 \pm 0.2	2.2 \pm 0.1	2.1 \pm 0.1
5	2-methoxy-4-prop-2-enylphenol (eugenol)	LG	77, 103, 164	0.69 \pm 0.03	0.59 \pm 0.09	0.70 \pm 0.05	0.68 \pm 0.11	0.87 \pm 0.13	0.94 \pm 0.14	0.71 \pm 0.19	0.90 \pm 0.11
6	4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (vanillin)	LG	81, 109, 152	1.5 \pm 0.06	1.3 \pm 0.1	1.2 \pm 0.2	1.3 \pm 0.1	1.3 \pm 0.1	1.2 \pm 0.1	0.99 \pm 0.05	1.0 \pm 0.0
7	isoeugenol (isomer)	LG	77, 103, 164	0.52 \pm 0.12	0.54 \pm 0.11	0.80 \pm 0.31	0.75 \pm 0.15	0.70 \pm 0.27	0.56 \pm 0.20	0.69 \pm 0.06	0.60 \pm 0.12
8	2-methoxy-4-prop-2-enylphenol (propenylguaiacol)	LG	103, 149, 164	0.91 \pm 0.16	0.75 \pm 0.23	0.83 \pm 0.16	0.87 \pm 0.14	0.52 \pm 0.12	0.96 \pm 0.24	0.50 \pm 0.07	0.60 \pm 0.06
9	1-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)ethanone (acetovanillone)	LG	123, 151, 166	0.99 \pm 0.26	0.95 \pm 0.18	0.80 \pm 0.20	0.61 \pm 0.02	1.2 \pm 0.2	1.0 \pm 0.3	1.4 \pm 0.4	1.5 \pm 0.0
10	acetovanillone (isomer)	LG	123, 151, 166	0.43 \pm 0.15	2.0 \pm 0.4	1.6 \pm 0.4	1.4 \pm 0.4	1.9 \pm 0.2	2.0 \pm 0.2	1.3 \pm 0.4	2.3 \pm 0.2
11	methyl 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzoate (vanillic acid, methyl ester)	LG	97, 153, 168	0.74 \pm 0.12	0.78 \pm 0.11	0.66 \pm 0.13	0.48 \pm 0.12	1.3 \pm 0.2	1.1 \pm 0.1	0.80 \pm 0.24	0.92 \pm 0.09
12	1-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)acetone (guaiaacylacetone)	LG	94, 122, 137, 180	0.67 \pm 0.12	0.77 \pm 0.07	0.59 \pm 0.10	0.60 \pm 0.04	1.0 \pm 0.1	0.67 \pm 0.04	0.66 \pm 0.19	1.0 \pm 0.2
13	1-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1-propanone (propiovanillone)	LG	94, 122, 137, 180	0.53 \pm 0.03	0.33 \pm 0.10	0.31 \pm 0.04	0.27 \pm 0.06	0.76 \pm 0.05	0.54 \pm 0.11	0.50 \pm 0.13	0.64 \pm 0.18
14	(<i>E</i>)-3-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-enoic acid (ferulic acid)	LG	133, 179, 194	0.67 \pm 0.16	0.51 \pm 0.09	0.40 \pm 0.05	0.45 \pm 0.05	1.1 \pm 0.1	0.73 \pm 0.08	0.71 \pm 0.17	0.80 \pm 0.12
15	1-phenylethanone (acetophenone) + 4-methylphenol (<i>p</i> -cresol)	LH	77, 105, 120; 77, 107	1.1 \pm 0.6	1.3 \pm 0.4	2.0 \pm 0.8	1.2 \pm 0.4	0.48 \pm 0.06	2.3 \pm 0.7	3.3 \pm 0.3	3.0 \pm 0.2
16	4-ethenylphenol (vinylphenol)	LH	77, 107, 122	3.0 \pm 0.3	2.3 \pm 0.4	2.7 \pm 0.1	3.2 \pm 0.1	2.4 \pm 0.7	3.1 \pm 0.4	3.3 \pm 0.4	3.1 \pm 0.3
17	2,6-dimethoxyphenol (syringol)	LS	93, 139, 154	1.6 \pm 0.1	1.3 \pm 0.1	1.4 \pm 0.1	1.6 \pm 0.1	1.7 \pm 0.1	1.7 \pm 0.2	1.8 \pm 0.1	1.9 \pm 0.1
18	2,6-dimethoxy-4-methylphenol (methylsyringol)	LS	125, 153, 168	0.79 \pm 0.06	1.1 \pm 0.3	0.82 \pm 0.08	0.89 \pm 0.15	1.1 \pm 0.2	0.71 \pm 0.19	0.75 \pm 0.16	1.1 \pm 0.1
19	4-ethyl-2,6-dimethoxyphenol (ethylsyringol)	LS	167, 182	0.61 \pm 0.10	0.48 \pm 0.07	0.38 \pm 0.04	0.33 \pm 0.04	1.1 \pm 0.3	0.56 \pm 0.02	0.35 \pm 0.11	0.63 \pm 0.19
20	4-ethenyl-2,6-dimethoxyphenol (vinylsyringol)	LS	137, 165, 180	0.88 \pm 0.08	0.99 \pm 0.018	0.69 \pm 0.15	0.81 \pm 0.14	1.4 \pm 0.2	0.95 \pm 0.03	0.91 \pm 0.13	0.94 \pm 0.13
21	2,6-dimethoxy-4-[(<i>E</i>)-prop-1-enyl]phenol (propenylsyringol)	LS	77, 151, 179, 194	0.38 \pm 0.08	0.55 \pm 0.13	0.50 \pm 0.06	0.38 \pm 0.12	0.52 \pm 0.21	0.54 \pm 0.11	0.46 \pm 0.07	0.64 \pm 0.17
22	4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (syringaldehyde)	LS	111, 167, 182	0.59 \pm 0.09	0.58 \pm 0.12	0.36 \pm 0.02	0.48 \pm 0.02	0.75 \pm 0.15	0.64 \pm 0.08	0.51 \pm 0.01	0.67 \pm 0.12
23	2,6-dimethoxy-4-prop-1-ynylphenol (propynylsyringol)	LS	131, 177, 192	0.53 \pm 0.05	0.39 \pm 0.16	0.44 \pm 0.08	0.41 \pm 0.07	0.74 \pm 0.28	0.53 \pm 0.04	0.37 \pm 0.05	0.44 \pm 0.15
24	propynylsyringol (isomer)	LS	131, 177, 192	0.08 \pm 0.01	0.16 \pm 0.02	0.28 \pm 0.01	0.24 \pm 0.06	0.49 \pm 0.29	0.06 \pm 0.01	0.50 \pm 0.19	0.49 \pm 0.08
25	1,3-dimethoxy-2-prop-2-enoxybenzene (allylsyringol)	LS	110, 125, 153, 194	–	–	–	0.05 \pm 0.00	–	–	0.23 \pm 0.02	0.29 \pm 0.09
26	1-(4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)ethanone (acetosyringone)	LS	153, 181, 196	0.93 \pm 0.06	1.0 \pm 0.1	0.82 \pm 0.05	0.97 \pm 0.09	1.1 \pm 0.2	0.88 \pm 0.09	0.87 \pm 0.14	1.1 \pm 0.1
27	2-(4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)acetic acid (homosyringic acid)	LS	167, 212	0.43 \pm 0.08	0.38 \pm 0.99	0.27 \pm 0.10	0.23 \pm 0.02	0.62 \pm 0.21	0.43 \pm 0.07	0.34 \pm 0.09	0.49 \pm 0.08
			Sum LG units	15.4 \pm 0.6 ^A	15.9 \pm 1.2 ^A	15.3 \pm 1.0 ^A	15.3 \pm 0.8 ^A	17.7 \pm 1.1 ^B	16.7 \pm 0.6 ^B	16.0 \pm 1.1 ^B	17.3 \pm 0.6 ^B
			Sum LS units	6.8 \pm 0.4 ^A	6.9 \pm 0.9 ^A	5.9 \pm 1.0 ^A	6.3 \pm 0.8 ^A	9.5 \pm 0.3 ^{Bb}	7.0 \pm 0.6 ^{Ba}	7.1 \pm 0.7 ^{Ba}	8.7 \pm 0.8 ^{Bab}
			Sum LH units	1.5 \pm 1.0 ^a	1.8 \pm 0.5 ^a	2.4 \pm 0.4 ^b	2.2 \pm 1.0 ^b	1.5 \pm 1.0 ^a	2.7 \pm 0.4 ^b	3.3 \pm 0.0 ^c	3.1 \pm 0.1 ^c

LG: guaiacyl units; LS: syringyl units; LH: *p*-hydroxyphenyl units; C: control; W: warming; D: Drought; W + D: Warming + Drought.

Fig. 1. Chromatographic traces for diagnostic ions (m/z) of the major methoxyphenols released by analytical pyrolysis from SOM. Labels in grey correspond to other non-lignin compounds that also includes mass fragments at that specific m/z .

cover. On top of that, the climatic treatments elicited a preferential accumulation of LH- moieties that would probably be related to lignin degradation and the accumulation of microbial residues (Ruiz-Dueñas and Martínez, 2009). Drawing out the effect of the habitat, this hints to a preferential microbial degradation since these moieties are less protected from degradation given their difference in chemical structure and feasible association with other SOM compounds (Clemente and Simpson, 2013).

4.1. Lignocellulose proxies

The LG/PS ratio was calculated to identify preferential degradation of either carbohydrates or lignin, whereas a higher ratio can be attributed to a preferential microbial degradation of cellulose (carbohydrates) and lignin accumulation (Rodríguez et al., 1997; Arias et al., 2005). It should be denoted by the H statistic (Table 2) the considerable estimated effect of the habitat as the main driven factor, stating that lignin dynamics are mainly driven to differences in the predominant biomass. Exerted effects by the climatic treatments are also observed with lower LG/PS values under drought, pointing to carbohydrate preservation along together with a restrained lignin decomposition (Dao et al., 2023).

As already mentioned, the LG/LS ratio in soil was found to vary with the source vegetation, reflecting partial preservation of characteristic

lignin patterns from biomass inputs to SOM (Dittmar and Lara, 2001; Otto and Simpson, 2006). This ratio provides basic information about the lignin structure, where a relative increase in LS- units implies more units with two methoxy groups and less free positions available to form strong carbon-carbon bonds (Ohra-aho et al., 2013). Greater values in open grassland can explain the higher contribution of grass-type biomass. Conversely, lower values for this ratio may indicate a preferential, partial degradation of LS- moieties, which are more easily degraded (less cross-linked) (Hedges, 1990; Adani et al., 2007). The effect of the climate treatments under the tree canopy was more remarkable, reinforcing the theory that there is a pointing out to a climate-enhanced degradation of lignin due to a biological stimulation of enzyme activities (Lu et al., 2022).

The content of Ph-C₁, Ph-C₂ and Ph-C₃ compounds is indicative of alteration by cleavage and oxidative cracking caused by microorganisms, with more altered lignin having higher proportion of shorter side chain methoxyphenols (Vane et al., 2001). Omitting the effect due to litter inputs/native vegetation into SOM, potentially caused by the two habitat-types, these lower values under the diverse climatic plots points to a lignin with longer and less alkyl side chain cleavage (Zheng et al., 2022).

The Al/K + Ac (aldehyde/ketone + acid) ratio is used as a proxy of an oxidative alteration of lignin-side chains of LS- and LG- units, where a

Fig. 2. Changes in lignocellulose proxies from compounds released after Py-GC/MS of soil. Values are mean \pm SE ($n = 4$). Uppercase different letters indicate significant difference between habitats; lowercase letters indicate significant differences among climatic treatments (Scheirer-Ray-Hare Test, $p < 0.05$). LG: guaiacyl-units from lignin; LS: syringil-units from lignin; Ph-C₁: phenylmethane-type compounds; Ph-C₂: phenylethane-type compounds; Ph-C₃: phenylpropane-type compounds; Ph-C₁ + C₂/Ph-C₃: ratio phenylmethane + phenylethane/phenylpropane; Al/K + Ac: ratio aldehyde/ketone + acid.

Table 2

Results of the Scheirer Ray Hare test of variance in relevance to the impact of the habitat and climatic treatments on the different lignocellulose proxies.

Proxy	Habitat (df = 1)			Climatic treatment (df = 3)			Habitat \times climatic treatment (df = 3)		
	H statistics	P-value	Significance	H statistics	P-value	Significance	H statistics	P-value	Significance
LG ^a /PS	9.56	0.002	**	4.87	0.041	*	1.46	0.692	ns
LG ^b /LS ^b	3.84	0.035	*	2.65	0.049	ns	1.70	0.644	ns
Ph-C ₁ ^c	2.27	0.131	ns	0.55	0.908	ns	4.56	0.210	ns
Ph-C ₂ ^d	0.69	0.687	ns	6.92	0.077	ns	0.44	0.931	ns
Ph-C ₃ ^e	1.37	0.242	ns	0.15	0.984	ns	1.89	0.592	ns
Ph-C ₁ + C ₂ /Ph-C ₃ ^f	2.75	0.197	ns	0.90	0.828	ns	6.31	0.097	ns
Al/K + Ac ^g	6.38	0.012	**	5.82	0.020	ns	3.01	0.390	ns

*, ** statistical significance levels at 0.05 and 0.01, respectively; ns: no statistical differences; df: degrees of freedom.

^a Guaiacyl-units from lignin.

^b Syringil-units from lignin.

^c Phenylmethane-type compounds.

^d Phenylethane-type compounds.

^e Phenylpropane-type compounds.

^f Ratio phenylmethane + phenylethane/phenylpropane.

^g Ratio aldehyde/ketone + acid.

decrease points out to a higher oxidation of lignin (Arias et al., 2005), and conversely higher values to a more recalcitrant lignin structure (Clemente and Simpson, 2013). In this sense, it is confirmed the enhanced lignin degradation under the tree canopy exhibiting the lower values, especially under the combined effect of warming and drought. It could be stated that these combined effects are promoting an increase in

oxidative enzymatic activity favouring alkyl side chains C _{α} -C _{β} bonds cleavage, therefore an accelerated decomposition of lignin moieties (Vane et al., 2001; Kirby, 2005; Pold et al., 2015). This matches with the higher LG/PS ratios under the climatic scenarios, confirming that higher oxidative lignin depolymerisation strategies are expected to better preserve the carbohydrates, might possible enable an efficient oxidative

Fig. 3. (A) Distribution of S/V and C/V ratios for the diverse habitat and climatic treatments. (B) Differences in lignin degradation parameters (acid-to-aldehyde ratios of the vanillyl-, Ac/Al_V and syringyl-type, Ac/Al_S) measured in the pyrolysis products of soil, according to each habitat (shape) and climatic treatment (colour). Vertical and horizontal bars denote the standard error of the distinct ratios. Dotted ellipses indicate distinction between habitats.

Fig. 4. Spearman's rank correlation matrices between lignin proxies calculated from pyrolytic compounds and microclimatic factors (n = 4). “*” indicates significant correlation at the 0.05 level; “**” indicates significant correlation at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

fractionation’ (Vangeel et al., 2020).

The calculation of further lignin proxies based on their classification as vanillyl, syringyl and cinnamyl (VSC) provided complementary discussion on these lignin dynamics, also to compare with diverse previous studies (Rasse et al., 2006; Spielvogel et al., 2010; Zhu et al., 2019). Relatively higher C/V values in the tree canopy may be indicative of the incorporation of biomass from leaves; however, control plots did not show significant differences, which effects of the climatic treatments could be attributed to a second process: preferential microbial degradation of lignin moieties (C-type) (Hernes and Benner, 2003). In regard to the S/V ratio, a decrease in this ratio especially under warming regardless the habitat-type may indicate a higher lignin oxidation degree of syringyl units (Pisani et al., 2015). Nevertheless, it should bear in mind that these ratios are not as useful and informative for assessing lignin decomposition as they are for describing predominant vegetation litter input into SOM.

Separately, the Ac/Al_V and Ac/Al_S ratios were calculated as denotative of side-chain oxidation, commonly indicated by higher values (Lobe et al., 2002; Otto and Simpson, 2006). Generally, Ac/Al_V values were higher and showed greater variations than those for Ac/Al_S, which primarily could indicate greater alteration of V-type units compared to S-type units. Moreover, vanillyl units may be more prone to degradation probably due to an increase of microbial activity and of enzyme pools as previously suggested (Pisani et al., 2016; Bao et al., 2017). The clear differentiation in Ac/Al_V ratios between habitats can be attributed to the influence of the dominant vegetation (Winterfeld et al., 2015). The notable effect of W + D by exhibiting higher Ac/Al_V suggests that V-type lignin units are more sensitive to degradation to a combination of soil warming and water scarcity, enhanced by the effect of the tree canopy. This effect, although less pronounced, is also significantly reflected in the open grassland for all climate treatments, most likely due to more limiting conditions to the ligninolytic microbial and fungal activities to

decompose and alter lignin dynamics (Dignac et al., 2005; Bahri et al., 2006).

In regard to Ac/Al_s, lesser differences are spotted though values are clearly differentiated from the control, especially in open habitat. Highest values in this ratio due to the effect of induced drought may be causing an increasing lignin oxidation of LS- units (Otto and Simpson, 2006; Bao et al., 2017). Contrariwise, lower values under warming scenarios, may point towards a less intensive degradation of syringyl units, especially under the tree canopy, when soil warming is just having a marginal impact. This finding contrasts to what has been found in previous research about the enhancement of favourable conditions for lignin degradation with increasing soil temperature (Spielvogel et al., 2007). However, further studies have pointed out that the effect of tree cover could favour the presence of more adapted and abundant lignin degrading microbial communities, with more favourable conditions for microbial and fungal enhancement (Thevenot et al., 2010). This could result in elevated soil temperature increasing oxidative enzyme activity, which would promote the breakdown of resistant SOM (Kaiser et al., 2010). Moreover, this effect could also be related to a higher availability of organic C under the tree canopy and higher litter accumulation, being this litter quality reduced under these abovementioned conditions (Nadal-Romero et al., 2016; Wei et al., 2022). On the other hand and contrasting to our second hypothesis, the relative lower ratios observed in the open grassland pointing to a low-degraded lignin could be explained by the absence of a microbial community readily adapted to the harsher conditions (Cerli et al., 2006).

4.2. Microclimate influence on lignin dynamics

Correlations between lignin biogeochemical proxies and soil temperature and water content has been diverted related to the habitat-type, as previous studies based on this experimental approach accounted for significant variations in these parameters between tree and open habitats (Hidalgo-Gálvez et al., 2022). Insignificant correlations are observed between the lignin proxies and microclimatic factors in control plots for both habitat-types, suggesting that following present conditions, there is little influence of microclimate on preferential degradation of certain lignin phenols and/or their side chain oxidation. It ought to be noted that S/V and C/V ratios are positively correlated regardless the habitat or climatic factor, which confirms the already stated strong influence of vegetation type and its simultaneous degradation. We discovered strong negative associations when we sorted the results based on climatic treatments, which suggests that scenarios including drought and warming are important drivers of the change of lignin moieties.

It is observed that soil temperature is negatively correlated with S/V for all climatic treatments in open grassland, confirming the preferential degradation of syringyl phenols (Hedges et al., 1988). We can observe the same trend beneath the tree cover with the exception of the drought treatment, which could be attributed as the protection of the tree canopy facing this factor. This finding related with increasing temperature is supported by further studies, proving that soil warming alter the transformation patterns of lignin, with enhanced, ongoing decomposition causing alteration of structural components (Amelung et al., 1999; Dao et al., 2022; Xia et al., 2023). Additionally, kinetic theory states that SOM decomposition rises as temperature in soil does (Conant et al., 2011). This finding was supported by a significant relationship between the degree of lignin degradation in syringyl units (Ac/Al_s) and soil temperature under warming in open grassland (Fig. 4).

In addition to temperature, soil moisture also affects to microbial community composition and enzyme activity, where lignin-degrading enzyme activity such as phenoloxidases and peroxidases can be enhanced (Bi et al., 2019). In 'D' and 'W + D' treatments there is a significant correlation between Ac/Al_v and Ac/Al_s reflecting thus the simultaneous oxidation of vanillyl- and syringyl- phenols beneath the tree canopy. (Dorado et al., 2003; Kiem and Kögel-Knabner, 2003; Schmitt and

Glaser, 2011). Lower soil moisture reduces microbial activity in general, leading to a regarded SOM degradation, including that of lignin (Liu et al., 2009). Hence, slower lignin degradation is supported by positive correlations between soil water content and Ac/Al_v and Ac/Al_s, especially observed in open grassland where the microbial community is expected to be already adapted to water scarcity.

The pronounced differences beneath the tree canopy can be explained by several reasons. On one hand, the abundance of fungi community in these sites is more efficient in lignin degradation (Dao et al., 2023). Moreover, it is provided to soils huge amounts of organic matter through leaf fall, prone thus to higher decomposition rates (Gallardo, 2003). Likewise, changes under the tree canopy –consisting in lower-light environments compared to open grassland– can affect to plant photosynthesis rate, and thereby, carbohydrate transfer (Heinemeyer et al., 2004), and the predominance of plants with root traits without mycorrhizal associations (Pérez-Ramos et al., 2010; 2021). Nevertheless, it should be accounted that according to the current knowledge about responses to temperature, the effects on decomposition rates arising from intrinsic molecular properties of organic matter might be strongly affected by factors such as physicochemical interactions with soil mineral and soil aggregation, among others (Duboc et al., 2014).

5. Conclusions

We have further demonstrated that Mediterranean savannahs are sensitive to climatic stressors that alter the dynamics in plant inputs to SOM and their degradation. A scenario of increasing temperatures and rainfall exclusion accelerate lignin decomposition in SOM measurably in relatively short time span (five years). Our study states that the stabilization of lignin and associated polysaccharides is primarily habitat-dependent, and climate-induced degradation of *dehesa* soils could result in promoting carbon losses by microbial degradation of lignin and associated polysaccharides. Interestingly, the role of trees far from buffering the climate influence is causing significant shifts in lignin dynamics, especially emphasized by the more advanced oxidation of syringyl units. Apart this major influence of the habitat, we detected strong influence of warming and reduced rainfall in altering lignin molecular structure.

The pronounced differences found with the lignin degradation indicators obtained with Py-GC/MS, suggest that this technique may be used as diagnostic tool for future environmental studies on SOM dynamics in other soils and situations worldwide. Although our experimental study provides relevant information in this respect, further studies estimating which organo-mineral mechanisms and possible microbial interactions are needed. We hence implied that the impact of lignin decomposition to be direct as climatic driving factors is affecting soil microbial aspects such as the microbial community and the enzyme composition and activity.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

L.M. San-Emeterio: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **M.D. Hidalgo-Galvez:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **J. M. de la Rosa:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **I. Pérez-Ramos:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **J.A. González-Pérez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest for this research: no known competing financial interests or personal relationships had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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